

Kinetic Study of Ag(I) Catalysed Oxidation of Glycine by Ce(IV) in Perchloric Acid Medium

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The kinetics of Ag(I) catalysed oxidation of glycine by ceric perchlorate in perchloric acid solution are reported. The reaction follows first-order kinetics with respect to each Ce(IV), glycine and perchloric acid. The reaction rate is found to be accelerated by Ag(I). Formic acid and ammonia are found to be reaction products. A suitable mechanism involving formation of a transient complex [glycine-Ce(IV)] has been proposed.

CERIC salts in various acidic solutions have been widely utilised for the oxidation of organic as well as inorganic compounds¹⁻⁸. In some cases the mechanistic approach has been based on the intermediate complex formation and in others the results have been interpreted by free radical mechanism in absence of kinetic or spectrophotometric evidence. Sometimes anionic species present in the reaction have also been considered responsible for deciding the cationic species of Ce(IV). Oxidation of some aliphatic acids such as formic acid⁹, lactic acid⁸ and acetic acid¹⁰ was studied by using ceric perchlorate only as an oxidant. The mechanism suggested by various authors is not uniform, indicating that wide varieties of mechanism are possible depending upon the nature of cationic species as well as substrates and any inference made on analogy would be naive. In this paper, we report the results and mechanism of oxidation of glycine by ceric perchlorate in perchloric acid medium in presence of Ag(I) as catalyst on the basis of product estimation and spectrophotometric evidence for the complex formation between glycine and Ce(IV).

Materials and method: The stock solution of ceric perchlorate was prepared by dissolving ceric ammonium nitrate A. R. (B. D. H.) in aqueous perchloric acid (Riedel, 60%). The acid strength of the stock solution was determined by McAuley's method¹¹. The stock solution of glycine (E. Merck) was prepared by weighing and dissolving in distilled water. Other reagents were sodium perchlorate (Riedel), sodium hydroxide A. R. (B. D. H.), ferrous ammonium sulphate A. R. (B. D. H.) and ferroin indicator (E. Merck).

The solutions of reactants were kept in a thermostatic bath to attain thermal equilibrium. The required amount of reactants were mixed together and aliquot (5.00 ml) was withdrawn from the mixture at different intervals of time and was added to a known volume of ferrous ammonium sulphate solution. The excess of ferrous was titrated with a standard solution of ceric sulphate using ferroin as an indicator. The kinetic runs were

studied using excess of glycine in the reaction mixture and the value of first order rate constant (k_1) was calculated by using the first order rate expression.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: A number of reaction mixture containing a known excess of ceric perchlorate over glycine was kept at 40° at 2M HClO₄. The amount of Ce(IV) left revealed 1 : 4 stoichiometry (Table 1) between glycine and Ce(IV) as shown in eqn. (1).

The product formic acid was identified by ascending paper chromatography using *n*-butanol with ammonia as solvent system and bromo-phenol blue as spot revealing reagent. The R_f value was found to be 0.50.

TABLE 1—TEMPERATURE 40° ± 0.1

[Ceric perchlorate] × 10 ³ N	[Glycine] × 10 ³ M	[Ce(IV)]/[Glycine]
1.00	1.50	3.96
2.00	1.50	4.00
2.56	1.50	4.04
3.00	1.50	4.12

Average value of equivalent = 4.03

Results and Discussion

The glycine-Ce(IV) oxidation was studied at several initial [reactants]. It was observed that the reaction follows first order kinetics in Ce(IV) which is obvious from the kinetic runs (Tables 2A and 2B). Contrary to our expectation the reaction rate decreases with increasing Ce(IV) concentration (Table 3). The unusual trend may be attributed to the formation of some unreactive polymeric ceric species at higher concentrations as suggested by Hardwick and Robertson¹² in high perchloric acid solutions.

The rate dependence of the reaction on glycine indicates first order. The rate of reaction increases

* For correspondence.

TABLE 2A—TEMPERATURE 40° ± 0.1

[Ceric perchlorate] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [Glycine] = 10.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [AgNO₃] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [HClO₄] = 2.00 M

μ = 2.56 M (Adjusted by adding suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate solution).

Time (min)	ml of 3.34 × 10 ⁻² N Ce(SO ₄) ₂ required by 5 ml of the reaction mixture	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0	1.84	—
10	2.18	5.98
20	2.52	5.55
30	2.82	5.49
45	3.28	5.58
60	3.66	5.45
80	4.14	5.65
100	4.58	5.52
120	4.98	5.49
150	5.48	5.40
T _∞	8.30	—

Average value of k₁ × 10³ = 5.50 min⁻¹
 Average deviation = ± 1.18%

TABLE 2B—TEMPERATURE 45° ± 0.1

[Ceric perchlorate] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [Glycine] = 10.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [AgNO₃] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ M
 [HClO₄] = 2.00 M

μ = 2.56 M (Adjusted by adding suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate solution).

Time (min)	ml of 3.34 × 10 ⁻² N Ce(SO ₄) ₂ required by 5 ml of the reaction mixture	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
0	1.84	—
10	2.34	8.05
20	2.80	8.03
30	3.22	8.08
45	3.80	8.00
60	4.32	7.98
75	4.76	8.02
90	5.16	7.66
105	5.52	8.02
120	5.84	6.98
T _∞	8.30	—

Average value of k₁ × 10³ = 7.97 min⁻¹
 Average deviation = ± 0.50%

TABLE 3—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [CERIC PERCHLORATE] ON THE RATE OF REACTION
 Temperature 40° ± 0.1, [Glycine] = 10.00 × 10⁻³ M,

[AgNO₃] = 1.00 × 10⁻³ N and [HClO₄] = 2.00 N, μ = 2.56 M
 (Adjusted by addition of suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate solution)

[Ceric perchlorate] × 10³ N— 1.00, 1.25, 1.67, 2.00, 2.50, 4.00, 5.00
 k₁ × 10³ min⁻¹ — 16.04, 12.45, 11.86, 9.78, 7.54, 5.53, 4.49

on increasing the concentration of glycine and has direct proportionality (Table 4).

The rate of the reaction increases with the increase in [H⁺] and have direct proportionality. The values of second order rate constant i.e. k₂ (k₁/[HClO₄]) shown in 4th column of Table 4 are almost constant showing first order dependence of the reaction on perchloric acid.

TABLE 4—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF TEMPERATURE, [GLYCINE] AND [HClO₄] ON THE RATE OF THE REACTION AT IONIC STRENGTH μ = 2.56 M (ADJUSTED BY ADDITION OF SUITABLE AMOUNTS OF SODIUM PERCHLORATE SOLUTION)

Temp. °C	[Glycine] × 10 ³ M	[HClO ₄] M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹	k ₂ × 10 ³ = (k ₁ /[Glycine] or [HClO ₄]) 1 mole ⁻¹ min ⁻¹
40	5.00	2.00	4.62	9.20
40	7.50	2.00	6.82	9.00
40	10.00	2.00	9.78	9.78
40	12.50	2.00	12.02	9.60
40	15.00	2.00	14.68	9.70
40	20.00	2.00	18.72	9.36
40	10.00	0.75	3.80	5.06
40	10.00	1.00	5.19	5.19
40	10.00	1.25	6.38	5.10
40	10.00	1.50	8.94	5.56
40	10.00	2.00	9.78	4.89
40	10.00	2.50	12.87	5.15
40*	10.00	2.00	5.50	—
45*	10.00	2.00	7.97	—
50*	10.00	2.00	12.37	—
55*	10.00	2.00	16.98	—

* [Ceric perchlorate] = 4.00 × 10⁻³ M.

In absence of Ag(I) ions, the reaction between glycine and ceric perchlorate is too slow to be measured. The effect of variation of [Ag⁺] ions on reaction rate is given in Table 5. Though no relationship is established between [Ag(I)] and k₁ values, the reaction rate is accelerated on increasing silver nitrate concentration. Measurements were made at 40, 45, 50 and 55° to investigate the temperature effect (Table 4). The energy of activation was evaluated from the Arrhenius plots as 15.10 ± 0.05 k.cal mol⁻¹. The entropy of activation was calculated and found to be -18.26 e.u. The variation in ionic strength (μ) of the medium, (adjusted by addition of suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate solution), showed positive effect on the reaction rate (Table 5). This indicates interaction between two similarly charged species.

TABLE 5—EFFECT OF VARIATION OF [SILVER NITRATE] AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) OF THE MEDIUM ON THE RATE OF REACTION AT 40° ± 0.1°

[Ceric perchlorate] = 2.00 × 10⁻³ M, [HClO₄] = 2.00 M and [Glycine] = 10.00 × 10⁻³ M

[AgNO ₃] × 10 ⁴ M	Ionic strength (μ)* M	k ₁ × 10 ³ min ⁻¹
4.00	2.56	6.33
5.00	2.56	6.94
6.70	2.56	8.16
8.00	2.56	8.72
10.00	2.56	9.78
12.50	2.56	12.74
10.00	2.03	7.84
10.00	2.75	10.68
10.00	3.25	17.90
10.00	3.52	20.30
10.00	4.02	23.62
10.00	4.50	27.52

* Variation in μ was affected by adding suitable amounts of sodium perchlorate solution.

The increase in rate with increasing acidity may be explained generally in terms of a model which

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